

Keywords:

#tool, #licence, #clearance #repository #RDM, #researchdatamanagement, #EOSCinPractice

Enabling the maximal re-use of data while ensuring IPR compliance.

An EOSC in Practice Story on the freely available NI4OS Licence Clearance tool, that facilitates clearing copyrights of any re-used research content.

The project involved

NI4OS-Europe (National Initiatives for Open Science in Europe) is a European Horizon 2020 project funded under Grant Agreement no 857645. The project aims to be a core contributor to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) service portfolio, commit to EOSC governance and ensure inclusiveness on the European level for enabling global Open Science. It focuses on supporting the development and inclusion of the national Open Science Cloud initiatives in 15 Member States and Associated Countries in the EOSC governance.

"This tool encourages open science and FAIR research, while respecting IPR and supporting greater transparency, research reproducibility, dissemination, as well as the transfer of new knowledge"

Panagiota Koltida, Senior Software Engineer, ATHENA RC

The Users

This EOSC in practice story is mainly addressed at **researchers or research organisations** who want to make their work available to the community, while protecting it with a compatible license.

The Challenge

Based on NI4OS-Europe's research, legal uncertainty about usage rights and high costs in clearance of licensing issues are very often a matter of concern when it comes to newly produced content but mostly the creation of derivative works, i.e. work that is produced based on other sources. Before sharing one's research it is important to correctly clear copyrights for any material that may have been used.

The solution

The **Licence Clearance Tool (LCT)** automates the licence clearance of derivative works and the selection of the most suitable licence for the users' resources. The tool provides a guided approach for establishing the proper open-source license required for the creation of a new (or synthetic) dataset, media, software etc. or for the re-use of existing unlicensed content. It proposes two workflows, one resource-driven for users that have a resource and want to clear derivate work licenses; the other is license-driven and it can be used when users have a target license and need to understand license compatibility with other resources.

LCT service access page

The service provider

LTC was developed by [Athena Research & Innovation Center](#), whose aim is to build knowledge and devise solutions and technologies for the digital society. The company is one of the **NI4OS-Europe** partners and a member of the [EOSC Association](#), which brings together key stakeholders in the European research environment to agree on strategies for the advancement of Open Science and to optimise the conditions for research outcomes, and ultimately, to make the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) a reality.

Why do I need EOSC?

Providing this tool on the EOSC portal, allows the tool to:

- » Gain visibility at European level
- » Reach a wider audience
- » Reduce barriers to research sharing and re-use

The users benefit from an easy to use tool and do not need previous knowledge or a legal background to access the resource. Moreover the following benefits can be gained:

- » Automation of the process of licence clearance
- » Usability for different types of products (e.g. data, publications, software)
- » No need for a legal background

LCT is available on [NI4OS-Europe service catalogue](#), a regional catalogue through which all the project's services are onboarded to EOSC

Access the LCT wizard tool as guest or authenticated user here, and is expected to be onboarded to the EOSC Marketplace

What the users of the service say

"We were very happy coming across the LCT in one of the OpenAIRE webinars, as it helps us to advise our postgraduate and doctoral students in assigning the proper license to the resources they upload in our institutional repository". Librarian, Patras University Library

The impact on society

In line with the other services produced by NI4OS-Europe, LCT encourages open science and FAIR research, while respecting IPR. This translates into greater transparency, research reproducibility, dissemination, as well as the transfer of new knowledge.

Across disciplines

LCT can be used in different domains and helps deal with IPR issues, checking for compatibility among different licences. Its use can therefore support and facilitate collaboration among researchers in various fields.

Future developments

The current version of LCT provides guidance and supports 73 existing standard open-source licenses. The work, however, is continuously evolving and new functionality will be added including user login/profiles and custom licenses in a future release.

Sustainability for an EOSC in practice

NI4OS-Europe's aspiration is that this resource and the others being developed by the project will be available even after the project's end. One important aspect related to making the resources sustainable is the fact that NI4OS-Europe offers all its tools as open-source solutions available through GitHub, so that they can be taken up by the communities that are interested in using and further developing the tools. Integrated in the NI4OS-Europe Catalogue, LCT can be used for clearance of licensing related issues during the onboarding process.

Future funding model scenarios

LCT is offered as a stand-alone tool, but also as part of the NI4OS-Europe Catalogue and onboarding processes, a fact that provides multiple sustainability pathways. The sustainability plans will be aligned with the current phase of the EOSC Association governance and the developments related to the EOSC Marketplace. The detailed LCT funding model will be released in the beginning of 2023.

Useful material related to this story

- » [LCT: a license clearance tool for research outputs re-use](#)
- » [Open Science Fair Demo](#)
- » [LCT Flyer](#)

Want to learn more about the other services being developed by **NI4OS-Europe**? [Read here](#)

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